

COMPOSITE BASED ON ACRYLAMIDE MODIFIED EPOXY-DIENE AND PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE SOOLIGOMERS

**Naibova T.M.,
Akbarova G.S.,
Hasanli P.M.,
Shirinov T.T.**

*Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Azerbaijan,
1010, Baku, Azadliq Avenue 34*

Abstract

Epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers were modified with acrylamide in an alkaline environment by the sopolycondensation method, their main indicators were studied and they were used as binders, and an anti-corrosion coating composition was prepared.

Keywords: oligomer, cooligomer, phenol-formaldehyde, epoxy-diene, modification.

Introduction

Oligomers or cooligomers, which belong to high molecular compounds, are used as linkers in the preparation of composites for various purposes. The rapid increase in demand for epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers used as binders is due to their many valuable properties. However, along with valuable features, the presence of certain missing aspects is undesirable both from an ecological and economic point of view. After solidification of epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomer, fragility, resistance to heat and burning, low adhesiveness, and most importantly, free monomers remaining in the finished product are undesirable. It was modified with acrylamide to overcome the shortcomings of these oligomers used as linkers. The shortcomings of sooligomers functionalized by chemical modification method have been eliminated, and the areas of application of the composite prepared on their basis have been determined [1-3].

Statement of the problem

The goal is to obtain a functionalized sooligomer with a new composition by modifying the existing oligomers in an alkaline environment with an organic compound containing an amide group through chemical modification, to determine the composition and main indicators with physico-chemical, physico-mechanical and spectral analysis, as well as to use functionalized so-oligomers as a linker. to prepare an anti-corrosion coating composition.

Methodology

For the purpose of comparison, the main indicators and spectral analyzes of unmodified epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers were studied in parallel. It was found that after the modification process, the main indicators increased, and the amount of free monomers decreased. (tables 1 and 2)

Table 1.

Key indicators of epoxy-diene oligomer and acrylamide-modified epoxy-diene sooligomer.

№	Indicators	Epoxy-diene oligomer	Epoxy-diene sooligomer
1	External appearance	Light brown	Light yellow
2	Amount of epoxy groups, %	17.2	11.5
3	Amount of volatile compounds, %	0.005	0.003
4	Gelatinization time, hours (120 ⁰ – 130 ⁰ C)	5-6	3-4
5	Molecular mass	500	748
6	Softening temperature, °C	80	85
7	Density, kg/m ³	1250	1320

Table 2.

Key indicators of phenol-formaldehyde oligomer and acrylamide-modified phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer.

№	Indicators	Phenol-formaldehyde oligomer	Phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer
1	External appearance	Light brown	Dark brown
2	Amount of free phenol, %	14.87	3-5
3	Amount of free formaldehyde, %	8.96	3.6-4.8
4	Amount of hydroxyl groups, %	17.28	10.61
5	Molecular mass	450	960
6	Degree of solidification, % (140 ⁰ C for 5 hours)	92.6	97.8
7	Softening temperature, °C	65	70
8	Density, kg/m ³	1186	1250

The fact that the functionalization process of existing oligomers by the copolycondensation method is a chemical modification is reflected in the spectral analysis (pictures 1 and 2).

Figure 1. IR spectrum of modified epoxy-diane sooligomer.

Figure 2. IR spectrum of modified phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer.

Thus, the IR spectrum of the epoxy-diane sooligomer modified with acrylamide shows the valence vibration of NH and -OH bonds in the absorption band of 3385.37 - 3851.23 cm^{-1} , the valence vibration of the CH bond in the absorption band of 2877.92 - 2930.13 cm^{-1} , 1541.91 - 1702.02 cm^{-1} deformation vibration of the C=O and NH bonds with the benzene ring, 1264.56 - 1396.49 cm^{-1} absorption band deformation vibration of amine groups, 1045.43 - 1182.57 cm^{-1} the absorption band 1 shows the deformation vibration of the -OH bond at 906.20 - 960.40 cm^{-1} , the deformation vibration of the CH bond, and finally the deformation vibrations of the epoxide groups at 763.30 - 836.57 cm^{-1} .

In the IR spectrum of the phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer modified with acrylamide, the intense absorption band at 3423.12 cm^{-1} indicates the valence vibration of -OH and NH bonds, the deformation vibration of the weak NH bond at 2092.81 cm^{-1} , and the intense absorption band at 1637.35 cm^{-1} valence vibration and a weak absorption band at 665.67 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of deformation vibration of the CH bond.

Modified sooligomers were studied in differential thermal analysis (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. DTA spectrum of modified epoxy-diane sooligomer.

Figure 4. DTA spectrum of modified phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer.

It is clear from the pictures that the destruction process of epoxy-diane sooligomer (picture 3) and phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer (picture 4) goes through three stages. In the first stage (at 200°C), the main destruction product is water, in the second stage, i.e. (at 200-300°C), breaking of functional groups is observed as the oxidation process takes place, and at this time, low-molecular compounds, mainly oxides, are formed. At the last stage of the destruction process, intense dehydrogenation and carbonization of the residue takes place. The coke number at 797.0°C in epoxy-diene sooligomer was 40.23%, and the coke number at 797.2°C was 46.36% in phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer.

It has been established that, regardless of the conditions of destruction, the presence of oxygen in the sooligomer has a thermooxidative nature and the bonds are broken. A coating composition based on modified epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde sooligomers was prepared and its main indicators were studied. The composition of the coating composition is as follows (k.h):

- Epoxy-dian sooligomer - 45.0
- Phenol-formaldehyde sooligomer - 50.0

Inorganic filler - 5.0

First, the sooligomers are dissolved separately in an organic solvent, mixed, and then a calculated amount of inorganic filler is added. It is mixed for 0.5-1.0 hours at room temperature until a homogeneous mass is obtained. The prepared coating composition is hardened by the thermal method (at 140°C for 4 hours), then the main performance indicators are determined. It was found that the coating composition made on the basis of sooligomers is resistant to water, oil, gasoline, weak alkaline and acid solutions. The hardness of the coating is 0.48 : 0.70; impact resistance 45-50 kg/cm; and its elasticity was in the range of 3-5 mm.

It is recommended to use it in corrosion protection of the equipment and facilities operated in the oil and gas extraction industry.

In conclusion, this thesis investigated the modification of epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers through the incorporation of acrylamide in an alkaline environment using the sopolycondensation method. The main indicators of these modified oligomers were studied, and their potential as binders was

assessed. Additionally, an anti-corrosion coating composition was successfully prepared using these modified oligomers.

Furthermore, the potential application of these oligomers in modifying thermoplastics and enhancing their properties was explored. The utilization of acrylamide-modified epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers as additives for thermoplastic materials holds significant promise. By incorporating these modified oligomers into thermoplastic matrices, it is anticipated that notable improvements can be achieved in mechanical strength, thermal stability, chemical resistance, and adhesion.

Results

1. For the first time, epoxy-diene and phenol-formaldehyde oligomers were modified with acrylamide and their main indicators were studied.

2. It was found that functionalization of oligomers with amide group compound eliminated their deficiencies.

3. A coating composition was prepared using the sooligomers with a new composition as a linker and its main indicators were studied.

4. Durability of the coating composition in different environments was checked.

5. It is recommended to use the coating composition made on the basis of sooligomers in

corrosion protection of equipment and devices operated in aggressive environments.

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